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Determinants of Family Planning and Population Control in Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Family planning is the core concept for controlling the rate of population growth which go beyond improvement in maternal and child health. This study aimed to identify the determinants of family planning and population control among resident of Tai local government area of Rivers State. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was adopted for this study with the population of 120, 205. The sample size for the study was 400 was determine using Yaro Yamane formula method. A multi-stage sampling procedures was adopted for this study which was done in two stages. A self-structured questionnaire titled: Determinant of Family Planning and Population Control among Residents (DFPPCR) was used to collect data. The reliability coefficient (0.82) of the validated instrument was obtained by correlating the two results using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings of the study showed that there was a very high negative relationship between socio-economic determinants of family planning and population control ($r=0.97$) which was statistically significant [$f(1,897) = 14785.70$, $p<0.05$]. The result showed that there was a very high extent of low positive relationship between the practices of family planning help and the reduction of population explosion ($r= 0.92$) which was statistically significant [$f(1,897) = 5462.32$, $p<0.05$]. The result of the study showed that there was a very high negative relationship between attitudes towards family planning ($r = -0.93$). The result of the study showed that there was a very high positive relationship between family planning as a determinant force for population control ($r = 0.87$). It was concluded that the exposure to family planning and usage was determined by several factors but specifically amongst respondents in Tai local government area of Rivers State, the following factors determined population explosion: socio-economic determinants of the people, knowledge of family planning and practice and attitude towards family planning. It was recommended that Government should ensure that health workers continue educate and sensitized the people so as to promote husband/partner discussion and male engagement in family planning to increase family planning uptake.

Keywords: family planning, population control, residents

INTRODUCTION

Family planning permit families, individual communities to plan their way of lives without subjected to sexual and social imperatives. Family planning is the core concept for controlling the rate of population growth which go beyond improvement in maternal and child health. Family planning is the information, means and methods that allow individuals to decide if and when to have children which involve a wide

range of contraceptives including pills, implants intrauterine devices, surgical procedure that limit fertility and barrier methods such as condom (United Nations Population Fund, 2017). Family planning allows people to attain their desired number of children and determine the spacing of pregnancies (World Health Organization, 2017). According to World Bank (2013) family planning is the practice of controlling the number of children in a family and intervals between their births and serve as an educational, comprehensive medical and or social activities which enable individuals including minors, to determine barely the number and spacing of their children and select the means by which this may be achieved.

United Nations Population Statistics (2011), the world population growth rates of the world's most populous countries (in decreasing order) are China, India, United States, Indonesia, Brazil, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Russia and Japan. However, Sub-Saharan Africa still faces the highest fertility and population growth rate at 4.71% in the world. Some countries facing population growth are Eritrea, Ethiopia, Sudan, Chad, Niger, Nigeria, Mali, Senegal, Gambia, Algeria, The Democratic Republic of Congo, Egypt, Colombia, Brazil and Mexico. However, Nigeria is one of those countries having high growth rate of population increase, with an estimated at 2.6 % (United Nation Population Fund 2016). This increase in population has caused many difficulties, especially in rural communities of the country because it has triggered limitation of resources along with a greater economic burden. In addition, the increased population has also resulted high fertility and also increased the chances of health risks for mother and child, leading to poor quality of life, and reduces access to education, food, and employment. In order to overcome the obstacles with increased population growth, family planning can play an imperative role in population dynamics that aids in economic stabilization of the country.

Access to the health service seems to determine the use of family planning methods. The family planning clinic or health facility maybe located far from the community that certain client may not have access to it. The studies of Asiimwe et al. (2014) further buttress that shorter distance to the health facility increase chance of family planning uses ($p = 0.02$). Also, older women were less affected by longer distance to the family planning service ($p = 0.013$) as compared with younger women in reaching for family planning service. However, distance to the health facility could likely alter the accessible of contraceptive. Health facility especially family planning clinic should be at-least 5 km to community so that the members of the community may reach out for their service. Access to family planning service may be essential to safe motherhood and improves the health of the populace. Since the first sex debut with a new partner is likely unprotected, the younger women are more sexually active may likely use contraceptive. Evidence shows that the use of contraceptives was positively linked with age and increases rapid with age of the women approaching 40-44 and a slight declination in age ranged 45-49 years (Palamuleni, 2013). To further buttress, married women and souses with secondary educational background and above are eight and six times more chance to contraceptive uses as compared with their counterpart without formal educational status (Ejembi et al, 2015). Promoting maternal education and fertility education will go a long way to strengthen the family planning practices.

Another factor that could determine the utilization of family planning service among the population is socio-economic status. The wealth of an individual or family would affect their family planning practices through ideation. Studies of Hussain (2011) reported that simple family (98.80%) accepted the family planning practices as compared with complex family type. The use of family planning is higher in nuclear families more than in joint families. Also, a woman that has job shows more probability of using family planning methods than those without job. Higher socio-economic status of the population may boost their sense of freedom and decision making process regarding family planning (Hussain, 2011). Women with little or no income status may not have interest in family planning service when compared with some of them with quality salaries or wages, good businesses or self-employed work. Studies of Palamuleni (2013) revealed that women without having children are 12.20 times less chances to use contraceptive as compared with women 5 or more. Also, family planning practice could be influenced by their occupation. Women without job or work status are 1.26 times are less likely to utilize family planning service than

working class women (Palamuleni, 2013). The chances of family planning practices may be improved if their socio-economic status increases.

In the same vein, the use of family planning service may be linked with belief system as well as religious background. Certain religion and culture do not permit the use of family planning methods whereas others do so since Nigeria is an ethno-religious society of which some families holds to Christian, Islam and traditional beliefs that may affect their way of life. Studies of Adebowale et al. (2013) showed more than half of Yoruba ethnic group (41.8%) had an increase use of family planning as compared with Hausa (3.6%) that religion is a strong predictor of family planning use ($P < 0.05$). Studies of Muhammed-Durosamorun et al (2017) showed a statistically significant different between religion (Muslim and Christian) and family planning use ($P .000$). The use of contraceptive is high ranged from 49.7% in 2008 to 54.92% in 2014 among Christians than the Muslim faithful (Avisah, et al, 2018). Furthermore, religious belief may predict the use family planning. Those who consider their religious beliefs while deciding the birth spacing methods were likely to adopt any method of family planning (Beson et al., 2018). It is plausible that some are women are religious minded in all their activities may attribute it to health care service. In Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State, women have not been able to utilize health care service especially family planning clinic because of their low standard of living and lack of awareness regarding the importance of family planning methods. The non-use of family planning method were observed among women of childbearing age because health care service are poorly available and highly affordable that low income people cannot obtain. It could be clear that family planning is not adequately available in the health facility for use. It is against this backdrop that this study unravels the determinants of utilization of family planning and population control among resident of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State. The factors responsible for the variation are at different hierarchy of individual family (cluster), and community (regional levels), embedded in socio-economic, demographic and cultural Society of Nigeria where Tai local government area is domiciled. Furthermore, several studies in Nigeria on of family planning services and population control were not proportional to assertiveness using advanced models. Since, it is crucial for population to be controlled and the survival of child and mother are not met. Hence, this study sought unravel the determinants of family planning and population control among residents of Tai local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to identify the determinants of family planning and population control among resident of Tai local government area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

In this, the following research questions were raised.

1. What is the level of population control among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. What is the family planning practices among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. To what extent does socioeconomic status determine family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?
4. To what extent does sociocultural factors determine family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?
5. To what extent does source of information determine family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?
6. To what extent does educational background determine family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?
7. To what extent does access to health facility determine family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the socio- economic status and family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State.

2. There is no significant relationship between the sociocultural factors and family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between the source of information and family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State.
4. There is no significant relationship between the educational background and family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State.
5. There is no significant relationship between the access of health facility and family planning among residents of Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

Area of the Study

The area of this study was Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State in Nigeria. It covers an area of 159 km² and at the 2006 Census it had a population of 117,797.

Research Design: A descriptive cross-sectional survey was adopted for this study. In this research, the researcher collected data on the determinants of family planning and population control in Tai Local Government Area of Rivers State and subjected collected data to statistical analysis without manipulating any variable in the study.

Population to the Study: The population of this study comprised of all residents of Tai Local Government Area which consisted of 120,205 (National Bureau of Statistics 2021).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size for the study was 400. Sample size estimation was done using Yaro Yamane formula method.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Total population

1 = Constant

e = degree of errors (0.5)

A multi-stage sampling procedures was adopted for this study which was done in two stages.

Stage one: sample random sampling technique was used to select 10 communities in Tai Local Government Area from the existing twenty two (22) communities in Tai Local Government Area without replacement by balloting. The selected communities are Sime, Nonwa, Gbam, Kpite, Korokoro, Borobara, Kira, Gio, Bunu and Botem respectively.

Stage two: systematic sampling technique was adopted to select 40 people from each selected communities for the study to make up the sample.

Instrument for Data Collection: The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: Determinant of Family Planning and Population Control among Residents (DFPPCR).

Validity of Instrument: Copies of the questionnaire alongside the objectives, research questions and hypotheses were given to supervisors and three experts in public health, reproductive health and measurement and statistics for face, construct and content validity. The corrections, suggestions and observations by the experts were used to design the final copy of the instrument. Hence, the instrument was valid for the study

Reliability of Instrument for Data Collection: The reliability of the instrument was established using test-retest method. 40 copies of the validated questionnaire were administered to the women of childbearing age in Oyigbo Local Government Area as a pre-test at first and after two weeks the same copies of questionnaire were re-administered for a post-test. The reliability coefficient (0.82) of the

instrument was obtained by correlating the two results using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Hence, the instrument was appropriate and reliable for the study.

Method of Data Analysis: The data so far collected and analysed with frequency and percentage table while the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation using the SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistical tools was used to answer the research questions and regression model was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The sampled size for the study is 400 but the analysis was based on 393 given the returned questionnaire rate of 98.25%. The results of the study are shown in the table below:

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between the different socio- economic determinants of Family planning and population control in Tai local government area of Rivers State?*

Table 1: Regression analysis on relationship between the different socio- economic determinants of Family planning and population control

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	Decision
1		-0.97	.94	.94	.72	2.66 Very High relationship

The table above showed the relationship between the different socio-economic determinants of family planning and population control. The result of the study showed that there was a very high negative relationship between socio-economic determinants of family planning and population control ($r=0.97$). The result further showed that lack of knowledge of family planning contributed 94.1% of the variance in the use of family planning mechanism ($R^2=0.94$). Therefore, the extent to which lack of knowledge of the socio-economic determinant to family planning and population control in Tai local government of Rivers State was very high.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between the practices of family planning help and the reduction of population explosion in Tai local government area of Rivers State?*

Table 2: Regression analysis on relationship between the practices of family planning help and the reduction constitute a determinant of population explosion

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	Decision
1		0.92	.85	.85	1.13	1.57 Very High relationship

Table 2 showed the relationship between the practices of family planning help and the reduction of population explosion in Tai local government area. The result of the study showed that there was a very low positive relationship between the practices of family planning help and the reduction of population explosion ($r= 0.92$). The result further showed that lack of exposure to the family planning practices and use has contributed 85.0% of the variance in population explosion ($R^2 =0.085$). Therefore, the extent to which the practices of family planning help and the reduction determine population explosion in Tai local government area of Rivers State was very low.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between attitudes towards family planning constituting population explosion in rural communities of Tai local government area?*

Table 3 Regression analysis on relationship between attitudes towards family planning constituting a determinant to population explosion

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	Decision	
1		-0.93	.87	.87	1.07	1.75	Very High relationship

Table 3 showed the relationship between attitudes towards family planning constituting population explosion in rural communities. The result of the study showed that there was a very high negative relationship between attitudes towards family planning ($r = -0.93$). The result further showed that people's attitude contributed 87% of the variance in family planning ($R^2 = 0.87$). Therefore, the extent to which attitudes towards family planning constituting population explosion in rural communities in Tai local government area was very low.

Research Question 4: *What is the relationship between family planning as a determinant force to population control in Tai local government area of Rivers State?*

Table 4 Regression analysis on relationship between family planning constitute a determinant force to population control

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	Decision	
1		-0.87	.76	.76	1.45	1.49	Very High relationship

Table 4 showed the relationship between family planning as a determinant force to population control. The result of the study showed that there was a very high positive relationship between family planning as a determinant force ($r = 0.87$). The result further showed that family planning contributed 76% of the variance of a determinant force population control ($R^2 = 0.76$). Therefore, the extent to which family planning constitute a determinant force to population control in Tai local government area was very high.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the different socio- economic determinants of Family planning and population control in Tai local government area of Rivers State.

Table 5: Regression analysis on significant relationship between the different socio- economic determinants of Family planning

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	7675.546	1	7675.546	14785.70	.00*	Rejected
	Residual	465.650	897	.519			
	Total	8141.196	898				

***Significant, $p < 0.05$**

Table 5 revealed the regression analysis on relationship between the different socio- economic determinants of Family planning and population control. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship different socio- economic determinant of Family planning and population control [$f(1,897) = 14785.70, p < 0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is a significant relationship between the different socio- economic determinants of Family planning and population control in Tai local government area of Rivers State was rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the practices of family planning can help reduced population explosion in Tai local government area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Regression analysis on significant relationship between the practices of family planning can help reduced population explosion

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	6986.857	1	6986.85	5462.32	.00*	Rejected
	Residual	1146.073	897	1.17			
	Total	8132.931 ^d	898				

***Significant, p<0.05**

Table 6 revealed the regression analysis on relationship between the practices of family planning can help reduced population explosion. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between the practices of family planning can help reduced population explosion [$f(1,897) = 5462.32$, $p<0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant relationship between the practices of family planning can help reduced population explosion in Tai local government area of Rivers State was rejected.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between the extents to which attitude towards family planning constitute population explosion in rural communities of Tai local government area of Rivers State.

Table 7: Regression analysis on significant relationship between the extents to which attitude towards family planning constitute population explosion.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	7109.141	1	7109.14	6178.83	.00*	Rejected
	Residual	1032.055	897	1.151			
	Total	8141.196 ^d	898				

***Significant, p<0.05**

Table 7 revealed the regression analysis on relationship between the extents to which attitude towards family planning constitute population explosion. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between extents to which attitude towards family planning constitute population explosion [$f(1,897) = 6178.83$, $p<0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between the extents to which attitude towards family planning constitute population explosion in rural communities of Tai local government area of Rivers State was rejected.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between family planning is a determinant force to population control in Tai local government area of Rivers State.

Table 8 Regression analysis on significant family planning is a determinant force to population control.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	6241.668	1	6241.66	2964.68	.00*	Rejected
	Residual	1886.387	897	2.10			
	Total	8128.056 ^d	897				

***Significant, p<0.05**

Table 8 revealed the regression analysis on relationship between family planning is a determinant force to population control. The Findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between family planning is a determinant force to population control [$f(1,897) = 2964.68, p < 0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between family planning is a determinant force to population control in Tai local government area of Rivers State was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussions of findings in Table 4.1 showed that there was a very high negative relationship between socio-economic determinants of family planning and population control ($r=0.97$). The result further showed that lack of knowledge of family planning contributed 94.1% of the variance in the use of family planning mechanism ($R^2=0.94$). Therefore, the extent to which lack of knowledge of the socio-economic determinant to family planning and population control in Tai local government of Rivers State was very high. It can be deduced from the findings of the study that because of Tai local government area were not exposed to the knowledge of socio-economic determinant of family planning and its applicability or usability there is therefore a higher degree of compromised population increase in the area. The finding of this study here corroborates that of WHO (2018) when it posited that family planning (FP) is a solution to control population growth and stop today's unsustainable growth. It went further to define family planning as allowing 'people to attain their desired number of children and determine the spacing of pregnancies. Aviisah et al. (2018) affirmed that women from high wealth index or rich family are 2 times more likely to determine good family planning practice to control population. It is achieved through the use of contraceptive methods and the treatment of infertility'. The study finding is also in tandem with Kopnina and Washington (2016) who emphasized that approximately 214 million women in developing countries who want to avoid pregnancy are not exposed to the idea of using modern contraceptive methods. Furthermore, Ebembe (2019) made a contrary view that the present debate of consumption or population has being the major cause of unsustainability. As previously stated, generally, the developed world over-consumes and the developing worlds are overpopulated. Family planning may be viewed as controversial, with historic coercive family planning policies standing in contrast to voluntary practices. Cultural, religious and economic factors attribute to the usage or non-usage of family planning services.

The result of the study on table 4.2 showed that there was a significant relationship between the practices of family planning can help reduced population explosion [$f(1,897) = 5462.32, p < 0.05$]. The relationship being positive indicated that if there obvious practice of family planning in Tai local government area it would contribute immensely to the population explosion in that area. The finding of this study gives support to that of Selamawit, (2015) who posited that the relationship between population growths is the idea that it would help in attaining sustainable development and fertility level. Hoyt (2021) added that good proportion of women using family planning methods were significantly predict high level of population growth of the family. The report argues that a reduction in growth rates is critical and that lower fertility rates are interlinked with sustainable development. The findings of this study is also in tandem with Adams (2009) revealed that our common future was built on the need to promote family planning that will fight population explosion in other to achieve economic growth. It also revealed that family planning focuses on poverty's pressure on the environment and the importance economic growth has to relieve on the populace.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between extents to which attitude towards family planning constitute population explosion ($r = 0.87$). The result further showed that family planning contributed 76% of the variance in population explosion ($R^2 = 0.76$). This finding could be explained by the fact that the understanding of family planning differ from one locality to another. Some may be far from its attainment than the others which makes family planning to be more significant with population explosion. The findings of this study is in tandem with that of Bekele et al. (2016) who reported that making a noteworthy improvement in modern family planning use is very obvious Ethiopia, but still availability and accessibility of family planning services vary between urban and rural areas. This

suggests that, in most places the current use of modern family planning methods utilization still remains low. It is, therefore, important to better understand the factors that affect modern family planning method use in all reproductive age group women in most localities (in this case Tai Local Government Area). Several studies have been conducted on determinants of family planning use in developing countries. In some cases, strong associations have been established between family planning use and some socio-demographic, cultural and economic characteristics of women.

The result of the study showed that there was a very high positive relationship between family planning as a determinant force for population control ($r = 0.87$). The result further showed that could attitudes of individuals towards family planning improve the tendency for population control would have been feasible. This finding is not surprising because attitude which is an individual disposition towards a given behaviour may be leading step to family planning practice. This finding corroborates other studies of Alemayehu et al. (2010) which conducted by the use of qualitative methods, but two studies have explored the topic. The study described social and cultural attitudes as factors informing people about their fertility preferences such as the marriage form, sexual norms and concept of family. Solanke (2017) revealed the relationship between one of their traditional fertility regulations, postpartum sexual abstinence and the marriage form polygamy. Studies of Marrone et al. (2014) claimed that the polygamous attitude have contributed to the relatively few number of children per woman because husbands can settle out with another wife while one wife is in a prolonged period of postpartum sexual abstinence thereby increasing the number of children in another form. It is obvious from this position that polygamous attitudes of men especially in rural African communities may be one of the major causes for the increased population, and was reported as an important cause by all categories of informants. This contradiction as clearly analysed in these studies has clear similarities with our positions in this study.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the exposure to family planning and usage was determined by several factors but specifically amongst respondents in Tai local government area of Rivers State, the following factors determined population explosion: socio-economic determinants of the people, knowledge of family planning and practice and attitude towards family planning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Government should ensure that health workers continue educate and sensitized the people so as to promote husband/partner discussion and male engagement in family planning to increase family planning uptake.
2. There should be a major emphasis of government on male partner views and opinions about family planning, in order to explore their role in supporting the family planning utilization and their participation on their use of family planning methods.
3. There is need to accelerate use of modern contraceptives in Nigeria. It is important to involve men in family planning, owing to the central role they play in household reproductive decision-making.
4. There is a need for comprehensive contraceptive information, which does not only promote contraceptive awareness but also ensure a positive perception of it.

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